

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF LITTLE CHILDREN'S MENTION

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Abstract. *This article is about the child's adaptation to the social environment of the primary school age and the changes that occur in them.*

Key words: *Thinking, child's social adaptation, L. Vgotsky.*

ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ УМНОСТИ МАЛЕНЬКИХ ДЕТЕЙ

Аннотация. *В данной статье речь идет об адаптации детей к социальной среде младшего школьного возраста и об изменениях, которые в них происходят.*

Ключевые слова: *Мышление, социальная адаптация ребенка, Л. Вготский.*

Children of junior school age are children from 7 to 12 years old, they are elementary school students. During these years, important changes occur in a child's life and activities. As a result, there are significant changes in their psyche. A child's entry into school is a turning point in his life. As soon as a child enters school and begins to study, the main activity in his life becomes studying. At school, the child systematically receives news, which is a source of knowledge on various topics that students are increasing day by day. As a result of the child's systematic acquisition of knowledge, the scope of his knowledge expands, mental processes develop, and at the same time, the child's emotional and volitional characteristics begin to develop again. The educational process at school itself makes new demands on the child's intuition, perception, thinking, speech and attention.[1]

In this case, the child may face several difficulties in developing his mental activity. Inability to accept the given tasks and difficulties in the development of the child's cognitive process may occur. But I believe that if the parent and teacher are always busy with the child, the child's acceptance will be normal. If they are asked more logical questions in the development of the thinking process, if they are given methods for finding differences, the child's thinking activity will develop better.

In addition to the above-mentioned diverse interests, individual interests of young students begin to emerge. Some students are more interested in painting, while others love music. One of the important characteristics of a child of primary school age is the presence of specific needs. In essence, these needs are not limited to acquiring certain knowledge, skills and abilities, but also reflect the desire to read.[2]

Based on the child's interests, we can develop his thinking and mental activity. First of all, we can develop the psyche of the child after knowing what he is interested in. For example, a child has a state of adaptation to different environments. Now the child who went to school does not get

used to school processes because he is used to the environment in his parents' home or kindergarten. The social environment is a new environment for the child.

Educational activities provide an opportunity for children of junior school age to meet the need to achieve certain achievements in learning, as well as to gain a place among their peers. It is to achieve this position or position that the child tries to study well. Children of this age constantly compare their achievements with the achievements of their peers. It is extremely important for them to always be the first. The motive of entering the competition in children during the junior school period is considered a natural psychological need, and this motive gives them a strong emotional tension. In fact, these characteristics begin to emerge from the kindergarten period and are clearly visible during the junior school period, as well as during adolescence [3].

During the junior school period, great changes occur in the child's relationship with other people. The child's communication should now be focused on a specific goal. In this case, the teacher constantly has an active influence on him, and on the other hand, it is the influence of the educational team. The teacher has a good opportunity to influence each student during the lesson. During the beginning of educational activities, the child's relationship with adults and peers begins to take a new shape.

The child has a little difficulty in expressing his "I" in relation to others. L.S. Vygotsky said that the individual behavior of a child is formed only within the collective life and under the influence of social relations.

The attitude of the teacher directly affects the student's activity. In elementary school, children accept new requirements and try to follow them with determination. For a child, the teacher is the main figure that determines his psychological state. Because his attitude towards the child has a direct impact not only on his attitude in the classroom, but also on his attitude towards his peers in general, and this attitude directly affects his relationships in the family as well.[4]

Also, these relationships determine the success of his educational activities. The attitude of the teacher to the child has a direct effect on his relationship with friends and family. It should also be emphasized that the nature of the new communication has a significant impact on the motives of the student's education at the junior school age, the development of moral qualities, the formation of self-esteem, and the level of the child's interests. shows. The success of children's educational activities and the formation of their personality largely depends on the characteristics of their relationship with the teacher, the degree to which they understand their position in the class, and their interaction with the group of students. .

According to psychologists, the laws of psychic and evolutionary development are as inviolable and universal as physical laws. Cardinal changes in the child's system of social relations and activities, corresponding to the changes in all systems and functions of his body, require the child to exert strong pressure and fully use his internal capabilities. These changes in a child who is ready for school do not bring negative consequences, on the contrary, they help him successfully adapt to new conditions. The attitude of the teacher has a direct effect on the student's activity.[5]

Children of junior school age are easily distracted, cannot focus on one thing for a long time, are impressionable and emotional. Cardinal changes in the child's system of social relations and activities correspond to changes in all systems and functions of the child's body, requiring the

child to exert strong pressure and fully use his internal capabilities. Changes at this age do not bring negative consequences, on the contrary, they help him successfully adapt to new conditions.

The attitude of the teacher has a direct effect on the student's activity. There are basically three forms of student activity at junior school age: physical, mental and social activity. Children of this age are very active. This physical movement is related to the fact that the child is interested in the things around him and tries to learn them. A child's physical and mental activity are interrelated, because a mentally healthy child is active, while a tired, depressed child is not interested in anything.

A child coming to school for the first time has a number of difficulties. First of all, it is difficult for them to obey several school rules. The most difficult rule for a primary school student is to sit quietly during the lesson. Teachers always try to make students sit quietly, but only a student who is inactive, passive, and has little energy can sit quietly for a long time during the lesson. It is difficult for a child who comes to school for the first time to fully understand himself and clearly know his actions. Only a teacher can set standards for a child, evaluate their behavior, and create conditions for matching their behavior with others. In primary school, students accept new requirements and conditions set by the teacher, and try to follow their rules. In educational activities, the child learns to act on the basis of human traditions under the guidance of the teacher, exercises his will to achieve educational goals. Educational activities require the child to develop speech, attention, memory, imagination and thinking to the required level, and create new conditions for the development of the child's behavior. The period of junior school is the period of transition to conscious and voluntary behavior. It is the period when the child actively learns to manage himself, to organize his activities according to the set goals. The emergence of new forms of behavior during the junior school period is directly related to educational activities. No teacher asks a child who comes to school for the first time to solve arithmetical examples and problems that he did not teach, but unfortunately, too many teachers ask them to study diligently, to be organized, responsible, and strictly follow the rules. they demand. However, these skills appear only after being taught certain habits and skills by the teacher. The ability to act voluntarily is formed during the entire junior school period. Voluntary actions, like the highest form of mental activity, are subject to the basic law of their formation. According to him, new behaviors first appear in common activities with adults, the child learns the possibilities of organizing such behaviors, and only then it becomes an individual way of behavior of the child.

Adults teach children the rules of how to study, play, go for a walk, and engage in other things in a practical way. So, in the family, the child occupies a new place where he is counted and consulted. The junior school period is a period of positive changes and renewal. Therefore, the level of success achieved by each child at this stage of development is extremely important. If at this age a child does not feel the joy of knowing and learning, does not acquire reading skills, does not know how to make friends, does not become a confident child in relation to himself, his capabilities and abilities, it will be more difficult to do these things in the future. , requires high mental and physical effort from the child.[6]

By this time, the child has achieved certain results in interaction with others, knows exactly what he wants and his place in his class and family. A child's imitation can be voluntary or involuntary. Involuntary imitation leads to mastering the behavior of the teacher and classmates.

In this case, the behavior is acquired unconsciously. It should always be remembered that a child can involuntarily imitate not only beautiful and desirable things, but also various negative looks and situations. Voluntary imitation requires volitional effort. In such situations, the child performs one or another behavior in a goal-oriented manner, tries to adapt these behaviors to a rule, an example, a standard. The teacher can develop effective social habits and feelings in the child through the characteristic of voluntary imitability. In any behavior and activity, the teacher evaluates the child, and the student learns to evaluate himself based on this evaluation.

What has been shown above is that the motivation field of the students during the junior school period changes, the general knowledge and motives in the preschool period are determined by the social ignition, and the desire to occupy the position of a student, that is, to go to school, and after this position is satisfied, a new indicates the emergence of educational motives and somewhat complex social motives of relations. By the end of the junior school period, students should have developed learning motives, that is, an interest in acquiring not only new knowledge, but also not only general laws, but also any ways of finding new knowledge. The formation of these motives is a necessary aspect of the preparation of children of primary school age for secondary school.

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